

Bromoarsenate(III) Complexes-I

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New method of preparation of double salts containing tetrabromoarsenate and amine hydrobromide of the type A_2AsBr_5 (A = Substituted ammonium cation) represented as $A AsBr_4 : A Br$ and A_3AsBr_6 as $A AsBr_4 : 2ABr$ in aqueous hydrobromic acid medium with their properties and characterisation has been reported.

POPOV¹ had investigated the reactions of arsenic tribromide with salts of organic bases in chloroform medium. He reported that four main types of double bromides differing in the ratio of $AsBr_3$: Salt of organic base were formed; the ratios found were 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 2 : 1 and 2 : 3. A few 1 : 3 and 2 : 5 complexes were also isolated. Jander and Gunther² while studying the solvent properties of fused $AsBr_3$ reported the formation of solvates like $Me_4NBr \cdot AsBr_3$, $Et_4NBr \cdot AsBr_3$ etc. In the present work the reactions of $AsBr_3$ with a few amine hydrobromides were studied in aqueous hydrobromic acid medium. The complexes obtained were of the types, 1 : 1 and 2 : 3 (arsenic tribromide : amine hydrobromide). Their preparation, properties and characterization are reported in the present article.

Preparation : The preparative method consisted in mixing a solution of arsenic tribromide with that of amine hydrobromide both in aqueous hydrobromic acid medium. Solution of arsenic tribromide was prepared either by dissolving arsenic tribromide or arsenic trioxide in hydrobromic acid.

Arsenic tribromide was prepared by refluxing a mixture of arsenic trioxide, sulphur and bromine³ at 80°; it was purified by distillation. Arsenic tribromide was then dissolved in dilute hydrobromic acid to yield the desired solution. Arsenic trioxide was heated with a slight excess of 48% hydrobromic acid than required by the stoichiometry of the equation $As_2O_3 + 6HBr = AsBr_3 + 3H_2O$. The mixture was cooled and filtered to remove the undissolved arsenic trioxide. Solutions of amine hydrobromides were prepared by mixing 48% hydrobromic acid with respective amines, the amount of hydrobromic acid used in each case was in slight excess to that required for complete conversion of amine to amine hydrobromide.

The solutions of amine hydrobromide and arsenic tribromide were mixed in the molar ratio of 10 : 1 (amine hydrobromide : arsenic tribromide). In some cases a precipitate appeared immediately, in others after a while (~2 hr) and yet in others after long standing (~8 hr). The solids so obtained were filtered and washed with acetone. They were then

recrystallized from 1 : 1 (by volume) mixture of acetone and isopropanol. The pyridinium compound could not be recrystallized because of its insolubility in the solvent mixture. The crystals were washed with diethylether and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Analysis :

The compounds were analysed for arsenic and bromine. The samples were dissolved in water (they hydrolysed in water yielding a clear solution containing arsenious acid, hydrobromic acid and amine hydrobromide). Aliquot of the solution was titrated with standard iodine solution for determining the arsenic content⁴. Arsenic was also determined gravimetrically by precipitating and weighing⁵ as As_2S_5 . Bromine was determined in the above solution by potentiometric titration with standard silver nitrate solution after acidification with dilute nitric acid⁶. The results on nitrogen content of the samples were obtained from microanalytical laboratory, C.D.R.I., Lucknow (India). Carbon and hydrogen could not be determined in these samples due to interference from arsenic (as per report of the microanalytical laboratory). The analytical results are reported in Table 1.

Physical Appearance :

All the solids were crystalline. Some of them were clear white and some had a yellowish tinge. Others were light to dark grey in colour.

Solubility :

Most of the compounds were soluble in solvents like nitromethane, acetone and isopropanol, but were insoluble in solvents like carbon tetrachloride, benzene and toluene.

Melting Points

The compounds did not show sharp melting points but had a range of about 2°. The melting point are shown in Table 1. The melting point

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TABLE—1 ANALYTICAL RESULTS (in%) AND MELTING POINTS

Compounds	Elements	Calculated	Found	M.P. °C.
1. Dimethylammonium tetrabromoarsenate(III)	N	3.97	4.20	192-194
	As	16.58	16.92	
	Br	72.57	71.97	
2. N-dipropylammonium tetrabromoarsenate(III)	N	2.60	1.90	98-100
	As	15.07	15.70	
	Br	64.43	64.06	
3. Quinoliniumtetrabromoarsenate(III)	N	2.66	2.52	157-160
	As	14.26	14.15	
	Br	60.96	60.30	
4. Tris(<i>n</i> -butylammonium) nonabromodiararsenate(III)	N	3.84	3.50	157-160
	As	13.72	13.55	
	Br	65.80	65.76	
5. Tris(methylammonium) nonabromodiararsenate(III)	N	4.34	3.87	267-268
	As	15.51	15.50	
	Br	74.54	74.22	
6. Tris(allylammonium)nonabromodiararsenate(III)	N	3.09	3.05	150-155
	As	14.35	14.40	
	Br	69.17	69.45	
7. Benzylammonium tetrabromoarsenate(III)	N	2.78	—	128-130
	As	14.89	15.15	
	Br	63.63	63.34	
8. Tris(pyridinium) nonabromoarsenate(III)	N	3.78	5.13	128-130
	As	13.49	14.00	
	Br	64.87	64.76	
9. Tributylammonium tetrabromoarsenate(III)	N	2.41	—	173-175
	As	12.89	12.75	
	Br	55.08	55.00	

of quinolinium tetrabromoarsenate(III) was reported to be 148°(1) but in the present work it was found to be 157-159°.

Chemical Reactivity

Bromoarsenates (III) are stable at room temperature in open. They are hydrolysed by water to produce a clear solution containing arsenious acid, hydrobromic acid and amine hydrobromides.

Discussion

The reported methods of preparation of bromoarsenates² required either the use of fused AsBr_3 or the use of non-aqueous solvent¹. The present method is a simple one requiring only arsenic trioxide, hydrobromic acid and various amines as starting material. It may be remarked at the very start though these compounds have been referred to as bromoarsenates(III), no direct evidence has been adduced to show that bromoarsenate ions like AsBr_4^- are present in these solids. In the case of a similar compound namely $\text{Cs}_3\text{As}_2\text{Cl}_9$ it has been shown by X-ray crystallographic analysis⁷ that the lattice does not contain discrete As_2Cl_9 ions but is composed of Cs^+ , Cl^- and discrete AsCl_3 groups. AsCl_3 groups are embedded between Cs^+ and Cl^- in such a way that all atoms are in approximately close packing. Thus this compound may be assumed to be double salt, $3\text{CsCl} \cdot 2\text{AsCl}_3$. It is likely that the compounds reported in the present work are also similar double salts.

However, recently evidence has been obtained to prove the existence of tetrabromoarsenate ion,

AsBr_4^- . It has been shown by Raman and i.r. spectroscopy that tetra *n*-butylammonium tetrabromoarsenate, $(n\text{-Bu}_4\text{N}) \text{AsBr}_4$ contains AsBr_4^- anion of C_{2v} symmetry both in solid and solution (in non-aqueous solvents⁸). In view of the similarity of the cations reported in the present work with that of reported earlier⁸ it may be assumed that the 1 : 1 complexes do contain AsBr_4^- ions.

It is noteworthy that the compounds formed in the present work are either tetrabromoarsenates (1 : 1) or nonabromodiararsenates (2 : 3). No penta- or hexabromoarsenates were obtained even though the ratio (arsenic tribromide : amine hydrobromide) was always 1 : 10 i.e. larger excess of amine hydrobromide was present in every preparation than required for the highest coordination of arsenic, say six, to produce AsBr_6^{3-} . Such a behaviour gives support to the view that the 1 : 1 complex contains AsBr_4^- and that penta- and hexabromoarsenates are not formed because of the steric factor—the larger size of bromine and smaller size of arsenic resulting in too much crowding around arsenic. A few 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 compounds are reported by Popov¹ but they may be double salts of arsenic tribromide and amine hydrobromide and may not contain bromoarsenate anions. However they may even turn out to be double salts containing tetrabromoarsenate and amine hydrobromide e.g. A_2AsBr_6 (A = substituted ammonium cation) may be represented as $\text{AAsBr}_4 \cdot \text{ABr}$ and A_3AsBr_8 as $\text{AAsBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{ABr}$.

The nonabromodiararsenates (III) may have structures similar to that of $\text{Cs}_3\text{As}_2\text{Cl}_9$ and AsBr_3 may be present as such in the lattice of protonated amine cations and bromide anions.

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